

Influence of attitudes, impulsivity, and parental styles in adolescents' externalizing behavior

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Abstract:	Diverse works have associated externalizing problem behavior with impulsivity, parental styles, and attitudes towards violence. The aim of the present study is to analyze the association between these variables and externalizing behavior. A cross-sectional correlational design was used with a sample of 252 adolescents, aged between 12 and 15 years, from the general population. The results obtained indicate a significant association of externalization with high impulsivity, ingrained attitudes towards violence, and inconsistent parental styles, as well as gender and age differences. The implications of these results and the influence of gender stereotypes in the differences observed are discussed.

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Abstract

Diverse works have associated externalizing problem behavior with impulsivity, parental styles, and attitudes towards violence. The aim of the present study is to analyze the association between these variables and externalizing behavior. A cross-sectional correlational design was used with a sample of 252 adolescents, aged between 12 and 15 years, from the general population. The results obtained indicate a significant association of externalization with high impulsivity, ingrained attitudes towards violence, and inconsistent parental styles, as well as gender and age differences. The implications of these results and the influence of gender stereotypes in the differences observed are discussed.

Keywords: adolescence, externalization, impulsivity, parental styles, multiple linear regression.

Introduction

Externalizing behavior problems include clearly maladaptive behaviors such as aggressiveness, psychomotor agitation, disobedience, and delinquent behavior (Achenbach & Edelbrock, 1984), which are very relevant because of the short- and long-term consequences, both for the youths involved and for society in general (Abada, Hou, & Ram, 2008). There is a growing body of research indicating that this kind of problem behavior is very common, affecting one out of every five children (Carter et al., 2010).

Problem behavior has great impact on school setting, where it is related to episodes of peer violence (Arseneault et al., 2006). In fact, there is evidence that exposure to this kind of experience can produce the onset of: (a) emotional and psychosomatic problems (Gini & Pozzoli, 2009); (b) low self-esteem, depression and suicidal ideation (Evans, Hawton & Rodham, 2004); or (c) antisocial behaviors, such as delinquent behaviors or drug abuse, which, in turn, cause legal, economic and social problems (Jiménez Barbero, Ruiz Hernández, Llor Esteban, & Pérez García, 2012).

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3 Impulsivity has been identified as a main predictor of externalizing behavior (Barratt,
4 1985; Olson, Schilling, & Bates, 1999). Eysenck (1993) defined it as the tendency to act
5 irreflexively without considering the consequences, and he related it to inhibitory deficits. It
6 has recently been reported that both functional and dysfunctional impulsivity facilitate
7 aggressive behavior, but dysfunctional impulsivity predisposes individuals to mistrust others
8 and to feelings of anger, fostering the expression of aggressive behaviors (Vigil-Colet &
9 Codorniu-Raga, 2004). However, some studies have indicated that impulsivity should be
10 conceived as a multidimensional construct, made up of diverse facets that could be differentially
11 related to violent behavior (Whiteside, Lynam, Miller, & Reynolds, 2005; Whiteside & Lynam,
12 2001).

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24 Impulsivity has been associated with the masculine gender (Chapple & Johnson, 2007;
25 Rutter, Giller & Hagell, 1998), which in turn is related to gender differences in the onset of
26 externalizing behaviors found in other studies (Beauchaine, Hong, & Marsh, 2008; Jackson &
27 King, 2004; Kjelsberg & Friestad, 2009). Some authors have indicated that the existence of
28 neuroendocrine differences in the sexes justifies a higher level of externalization in males
29 (Shirtcliff, Granger, Booth, & Johnson, 2005), whereas other works have supported the
30 influence of family socialization and parental styles in this phenomenon (Eisenberg et al., 2001;
31 Maccoby & Martin, 1983).

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42 Cognitive-social theory (Bandura, 2001) has had great impact in the past few decades.
43 This theory postulates that diverse variables intervene in the learning of externalizing behavior
44 patterns: environment, personality, and the psychological maturation process must converge to
45 form memory structures and processes that, in turn, influence cognitive strategies used in
46 various social situations (Bandura, 2006; Crick & Dodge, 1994). According to this model,
47 individuals choose certain strategies as a function of their capacity, self-efficacy, expectations of
48 success, or internal norms, such as attitudes and moral values (Bandura, 2001). Some works
49 have found evidence of an association between violent behavior and tolerant attitudes towards
50 violence (Jiménez Barbero et al., 2012; Josephson & Prolix, 2008), and it has been reported that
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3 the modification of youngsters' attitudes could reduce the risk of such behaviors (Hamish &
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5 Guerra, 2002; Zuni, Downey, & Rosen, 2004).
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8 From this cognitive-social approach, it is notable that many child socialization theories
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10 have proposed a close relation between parental styles and the onset of externalizing behavior
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12 (Aunola & Nurmi, 2005; Rothbaum & Weisz, 1994; Windlin & Kuntshce, 2011). The
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14 traditional typology of parental styles elaborated by Baumrind (1991) presents four patterns as a
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16 function of affect and control: (a) authoritative, with high levels of affect and control; (b)
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18 authoritarian, with high control and low affect; (c) permissive, with high affect and low control;
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20 and (d) negligent, with low control and low affect. It has been reported that parental style
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22 directly influences school violence. In general, authoritarian parental styles, based on coercion
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24 and harshness, have been related to poor cognitive reasoning, which is associated with
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26 expressions of aggressive behavior (Dodge & Crick, 1990). In fact, recent studies report that an
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28 authoritarian maternal style and exposure to violence are usually associated with this kind of
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30 behavior (Mitchell et al., 2009). However, although most authors relate problem behavior to
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32 authoritarian styles, significant relations have also been found with inconsistent parental styles
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34 (Dwairy, 2008).
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37 The literature reviewed has shown that externalizing behavior is mainly associated with
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39 impulsivity, although parental styles and attitudes towards violence could have a modulating
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41 effect on these behaviors. Hence, this work proposes the following goals: (a) to study the degree
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43 of association of externalizing behavior problems with the above-mentioned predictors, (b) to
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45 determine the existence of gender differences in externalizing behavior problems, and (c) to
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47 analyze the variables associated with externalizing behavior from two dimensions: problem
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49 behavior and verbal aggressiveness.
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56 **Methods**

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Design and description of the sample

We used a cross-sectional design with a sample of nonclinical adolescents from a Secondary Education Institute, assessed during the 2010-2011 school term, within the framework of a research project financed by the Regional Government. We selected this school because it was in a neighborhood with a population of similar sociodemographic characteristics to those of the rest of the urban population of that area.

The study comprised students aged between 12-15 years. Adolescents who presented special educational needs or who were in psychological or psychiatric treatment were excluded from the study. Participants who did not pass a sincerity questionnaire included in the instrument were also ruled out of the study. Out of 268 potentially eligible students, 16 were eliminated due to diverse exclusion criteria, so the final sample comprised 252 participants: 130 boys (51.58%) and 122 girls (48.41%), with ages between 12-15 years. The mean and median age of the adolescents was 13.54 and 14, respectively ($SD = 0.85$). Table 1 shows that, among the fathers, there was a predominance of those who had university and middle studies (39.68 and 31.74%, respectively), whereas among the mothers, those who had completed university studies predominated (48.8%). Most of the children lived with both parents (84.12%).

INSERT TABLE 1 ABOUT HERE

Measures

The protocol employed includes a questionnaire made up of 201 items, which was completed by adolescents sampled, and which requires about 35 minutes in most cases. This instrument collected the sociodemographic variables (age, sex, parents' educational level, family structure), as well as the variables of the study. The project was approved by the Ethics and Clinical Research Committee of the University Hospital "Virgen de la Arrixaca" (Murcia- Spain).

Sociodemographic variables

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3 This included age, gender, family co-existence, and parents' educational level. Age was
4 categorized into two groups: I (12 and 13 years) and II (14 and 15 years). Family co-existence
5 was divided into 4 categories: (1) *I live with both my parents*, (2) *I live with my mother*, (3) *I*
6 *live with my father*, or (4) *I don't live with my parents*. Parents' educational level was
7 categorized as: (1) no studies, (2) elementary studies, (3) middle studies, and (4) university
8 studies.
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17 *Externalization.* We used the Youth Self-Report (YSR; Achenbach, 1991), a self-administered
18 questionnaire designed to obtain information directly from children and adolescents between 11
19 and 18 years about diverse competences and behavior problems. It has two parts: the first part
20 assesses sports, academic and social competences, and the second part is made up of 112 items
21 that assess prosocial behaviors and behavior problems.
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27 For the present study, we used the items that measure the factors Verbal Aggressiveness
28 and Behavior Problems, due to their greater internal consistency, according to validation studies
29 in Spanish with this instrument (Lemos Giráldez, Vallejo Seco, & Sandoval Mena, 2002).
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35 *Impulsivity.* We used the Impulsivity Scale (Barratt, 1985), in its validated Spanish version
36 (Luengo, Carrillo de la Peña, & Otero, 1991), which has levels of internal consistency of about
37 .90. We used the motor subscale of this instrument because we considered it the most
38 appropriate to the purposes of the study.
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45 *Attitudes towards violence.* We used the "Cuestionario de Actitud Hacia la Violencia" (CAHV-
46 25; in English, the Questionnaire of Attitudes towards Violence; Ruiz Hernández, Llor, Puebla,
47 & Llor Esteban, 2009). This instrument has 4 factors: Violence as a form of Fun (7 items,
48 Cronbach $\alpha = .78$); Violence to improve Self-esteem (5 items, Cronbach $\alpha = .78$); Violence to
49 Cope with Problems and Social Relations (6 items, Cronbach $\alpha = .68$); and Violence perceived
50 as Legitimate (7 items, Cronbach $\alpha = .72$). The level of total internal consistency of the
51 instrument was .90.
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Parental style. To study this variable, the adolescents completed the “Cuestionario sobre Estilos Disciplinarios de los Padres” (in English, the Questionnaire of Parents' Disciplinary Styles), elaborated and validated by Torrente Hernández and Vazsonyi (2008). This self-administered instrument is made up of 52 items, which classify educational styles as inductive, authoritarian, permissive, and over-protective, based on the educational patterns described by Baumrind (1991). The reliability analyses of the questionnaire has provided Cronbach alpha values of $\alpha = .77$ for paternal styles and $\alpha = .69$ for maternal styles.

Sincerity. Due to the problems of sincerity usually present in adolescents' self-reports, two control methods were included in the instrument: the Sincerity subscale included in the “Cuestionario de Auto-Control Infantil y Adolescente” (CACIA; in English, the Children's and Adolescents' Self- Control Questionnaire; Capafons & Silva, 1998), which we consider appropriate because it is short (only 14 items), simple, and easy to understand; and one self-reported sincerity question (“*How would you rate your sincerity?*”).

Statistical analyses

We performed Student's *t*-test to examine the sociodemographic variables. To examine the psychosocial variables, we performed Pearson correlation analysis and, in order to determine a predictive model of externalizing behavior, we used stepwise multiple linear regression analysis with the variables previously identified as relevant. The level of significance was defined for values of $p < .05$.

Results

Significant differences as a function of adolescents' age and gender were obtained. In the case of age, the mean scores in Attitudes towards Violence were higher in the group of 14-15-year-old

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3 children ($p < .001$). Significant differences by age were also found in the permissive maternal
4 educational style, which obtained a higher score among the 12-13-year-old children ($t = -2.237$,
5 $p < .05$). With regard to the dependent variable externalizing behavior, we obtained age
6 differences in the factor Verbal Aggressiveness, in which the 14-15-year-old children scored
7 higher ($t = -2.476$, $p < .05$).
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12 Gender differences in the variable impulsivity were found, with higher scores among
13 the girls ($t = -2.298$, $p < .05$). In the dependent variable externalizing behavior, the boys
14 obtained significantly higher scores in the factor Behavior Problems, ($t = 2.279$, $p < .005$),
15 whereas the girls scored higher in Verbal Aggressiveness ($t = -2.043$, $p < .05$).
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20 As seen in Table 2, there were significant correlations between Verbal Aggressiveness
21 and all the factors of the variable attitudes towards violence, range from .460 to .497 ($p < .01$) as
22 well as with the variable impulsivity ($r = .625$, $p < .01$). Verbal Aggressiveness also correlated
23 positively with the authoritarian, permissive, and over-protective maternal, (range from .199 to
24 .482, $p < .01$), and paternal educational styles (range from .139 to .343, $p < .05$).
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29 Moreover, Behavior Problems correlated significantly with all the factors of attitudes
30 towards violence (range from .555 to .601, $p < .01$), and impulsivity ($r = .570$, $p < .01$). With
31 regard to parental styles, Behavior Problems correlated negatively with maternal ($r = -.226$, $p <$
32 $.01$) and paternal ($r = -.187$, $p < .01$) inductive styles, and positively with maternal ($r = .583$, p
33 $< .01$) and paternal ($r = .359$, $p < .01$) authoritarian styles, and with maternal ($r = .273$, $p <$
34 $.01$) and paternal ($r = .283$, $p < .01$) permissive styles.
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50 In the analysis, we included the variables that were relevant after performing the
51 bivariate correlational analyses. The regression model provides the following results for each
52 one of the factors of the variable externalizing behavior, adjusted by gender.
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56 *Verbal Aggressiveness.* In male children, Verbal Aggressiveness was associated with
57 impulsivity ($\beta = .403$, $p < .001$) and with attitudes towards violence as a way to improve self-
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3 esteem ($\beta = .308, p < .001$). The goodness of fit of the model (corrected determination
4 coefficient) was adjusted $R^2 = .365, p < .001$.

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In contrast, Verbal Aggressiveness in females was associated with impulsivity ($\beta =$
.554, $p < .001$) and with attitudes towards violence as a form of social skill ($\beta = .334, p < .001$),
although in this case, the goodness fit was higher (adjusted $R^2 = .500, p < .001$).

Behavior Problems. The regression model of the boys explains 57.5% of the variance
(adjusted $R^2 = .575, p < .001$), and indicates that Behavior Problems are associated with
impulsivity ($\beta = .334, p < .001$), attitudes towards violence as a form of social skill ($\beta = .329, p$
 $< .001$), and authoritarian maternal ($\beta = .423, p < .001$) and paternal ($\beta = -.231, p < .005$)
educational styles. Similar results were obtained in girls (adjusted $R^2 = .568, p < .001$), although
in this case, the variables that best fit the regression model were: attitudes towards violence as a
form of fun ($\beta = .447, p < .001$), impulsivity ($\beta = .296, p < .001$), permissive paternal ($\beta = .179,$
 $p < .005$), and authoritarian maternal style ($\beta = .177, p < .05$). (See table 3).

INSERT TABLE 3 ABOUT HERE

Discussion

Our study provides evidence of the importance of impulsivity in the diverse types of
adolescents' externalizing behavior, which is consistent with prior research that concludes that
impulsivity foments people's aggressive reactions, especially anger when dealing with events
that are perceived as stressful (Eisenberg et al., 2004). Thus, intervention on this dimension is
essential to address externalizing behavior problems, implying an approach focused on
enhancing parents' skills and improving adolescents' social skills, and even
psychopharmacological treatment (Turgay, 2005).

However, we found gender differences, both in educational styles and in attitudes
towards violence, in the diverse types of externalizing behavior assessed.

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3 Firstly, the results relate Verbal Aggressiveness to impulsivity and to attitudes towards
4 violence. In the case of the boys, we observed greater influence of attitudes oriented to
5 promoting self-esteem. However, among the girls, this type of behaviors seems to be associated
6 with attitudes towards violence as a way to cope with problems and social relations. These
7 differences in attitudes could be related to the effect of traditional gender stereotypes,
8 transmitted through primary and secondary socialization processes, in which aggressive
9 behavior is identified with domination of others in the case of boys (Cowie, 2000), and the use
10 of indirect violence as a response to situational pressure in the case of girls (Olweus, 2005).
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15 Secondly, externalization manifested as Behavior Problems appears in males with a
16 high level of impulsivity, who use violence as a way to solve problems and who have received
17 an authoritarian educational style from their mothers. With regard to this result, Tolan (2007)
18 found that the use of coercive educational styles is usually associated with violence in the
19 family sphere. Continued exposure to violent patterns could act as a kind of social modeling,
20 favoring greater predisposition to use violence to resolve conflicts. However, our results also
21 indicate that the paternal authoritarian style has an inhibitory effect on this type of behaviors.
22 Apparently, boys show a tendency to rebel against maternal authority, whereas, in contrast, they
23 accept the authoritarian educational customs of the father. This phenomenon could be related to
24 fathers' lesser involvement in their adolescent children's socialization: the fact that it is the
25 mother who habitually sets limits on her children's behavior, with the fathers intervening only
26 occasionally, could make adolescents tend to assign more "value" to paternal disciplinary acts,
27 to the detriment of the maternal ones. To this is added the effect of the above-mentioned gender
28 stereotype, which would induce boys' rejection of maternal authoritarian acts.
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34 In girls, this type of externalization is related to a higher level of impulsivity, attitudes
35 towards violence as a form of fun, and inconsistent interparental educational styles. In this
36 sense, the constant reception of contradictory, permissive, or indulgent messages from the
37 father, and coercive or authoritarian messages from the mother could decrease girls' ability to
38 discern the difference between what is or is not socially acceptable. This could reduce their
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3 empathic capacity towards their peers and favor the tendency to minimize the negative effects of
4 violence, which is accepted as just another way of having fun.
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7 In general, the models suggested by the results obtained could be understood from the
8 perspective of gender stereotypes and their effect on adolescents' attitudes, and family
9 socialization, which assigns an active, intrepid, resolute role to males, and a prudent and discrete
10 role to females (Young & Sweeting, 2004). Likewise, our results are in line with other works
11 that relate aggressive behaviors to the maternal authoritarian style (Mitchell et al., 2009), and
12 that underline the role of inconsistent educational styles in the development of behavior
13 problems . The presence of ingrained attitudes towards violence would contribute to the
14 adolescents' developing externalizing behaviors that could appear impulsively, when
15 adolescents are incapable of anticipating the possible consequences of their acts, or
16 intentionally, when, after appraising the consequences, they consider them acceptable (Dodge &
17 Petit, 2003).
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29 Lastly, in view of the relations found between gender and parental educational style, we
30 think it would be interesting to develop studies aimed at analyzing the differences in the
31 educational patterns practiced by parents as a function of their children's gender, and the
32 implications in the development of attitudes towards violence. The methodology employed in
33 this work does not allow us to establish causal relations among the variables, so this analysis
34 should be carried out by means of other methodological designs, like randomized clinical trials,
35 with larger sample sizes.
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Table 1
Sociodemographic Variables

Variables	N	(%)
Age		
12-13	118	(46.82)
14-15	134	(53.17)
Gender		
Boys	130	(51.6)
Girls	122	(48.4)
Father's educational level		
No studies	9	(3.57)
Elementary studies	63	(25)
Middle studies	80	(31.74)
University studies	100	(39.68)
Mother's educational level		
No studies	10	(3.96)
Elementary studies	66	(26.19)
Middle studies	53	(21)
University studies	123	(48.8)
With whom do you live?		
I live with my father and my mother	212	(84.12)
I live with my mother	32	(12.69)
I live with my father	4	(1.58)
I don't live with my parents	4	(1.58)

Table 2 Pearson Correlations among the Factors of the Dependent Variable Externalizing Behavior and the Predictor Variables Attitudes towards Violence, Impulsivity, and Educational Styles

Externalizing Behavior	Impulsivity	Attitudes towards Violence				Maternal Educational Styles				Paternal Educational Styles			
		Fun	Self-esteem	Social skills	Legitimate	Inductive	Authoritarian	Permissive	Over-protective	Inductive	Authoritarian	Permissive	Over-protective
Verbal aggression	.625**	.497**	.460**	.489**	.485**	-.113	.482**	.199**	.213**	-.119	.343**	.165*	.139*
Behavioral problems	.570**	.601**	.573**	.563**	.555**	-.226**	.583**	.273**	.044	-.187**	.359**	.283**	.092

*p < .05. **p < .001.

Table 3

Multiple Linear Regression Model for the Factors of Externalizing Behavior, "Verbal Aggressiveness", and "Behavior Problems".

Factors of Externalizing Behavior	Sex	Predictor variables*	Regression coefficients					Goodness of fit			Regression ANOVA	
			B	S	β	t	p	R	R ²	S _e	F	p
Verbal Aggressiveness	Boys	Constant	.253	.304		.831	.407	.612	.365	.71034	38.032	.000
		Impulsivity	.813	.161	.403	5.063	.000					
		Violence-Self-esteem	.341	.088	.308	3.875	.000					
	Girls	Constant	-.160	.272		-.589	.557					
		Impulsivity	.945	.113	.554	8.352	.000					
		Violence-Social Skill	.443	.088	.334	5.047	.000					
Behavior Problems	Boys	Constant	-.643	.255		-2.518	.013	.767	.575	.48875	44.651	.000
		Impulsivity	.568	.117	.334	4.834	.000					
		Violence-Social Skill	.303	.061	.329	4.941	.000					
		Authoritarian-Maternal	.619	.119	.423	5.187	.000					
		Authoritarian-Paternal	-.349	.112	-.231	-3.109	.002					
	Girls	Constant	-.710	.217		-3.279	.001					
		Violence-Fun	.300	.045	.447	6.673	.000					
		Impulsivity	.300	.070	.296	4.288	.000					
		Permissive-Paternal	.185	.063	.179	2.936	.004					
		Authoritarian-Maternal	.195	.077	.177	2.525	.013					

Note. B = nonstandardized regression coefficient; SE = standard error; β = standardized regression coefficient; R = multiple correlation coefficient; R² = determination coefficient; S_e = standard estimation error.

* The predictor variables are arranged in descending order as a function of their relevance for the fit of the model.